

Simultaneous Synthesis of Nudiflorine and Ricinidine*

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In reporting our work on the structure of nudiflorine¹, the alkaloid amide of *Trewia nudiflora* Linn., the origin of both nudiflorine and ricinidine from a common biogenetic precursor, viz., nicotinic acid (I: X=CO₂H), was mentioned. We now report a synthesis in which both these compounds are simultaneously formed, thus lending further support to our biogenetic scheme¹.

Nicotinamide (I: X=CONH₂) was dehydrated to 3-cyanopyridine (I: X=CN) according to La Forge² and it was then treated with dimethyl sulphate at the reflux temperature. The methosulphate formed was dissolved in water and treated with potassium ferricyanide at 0-5°, following the method of Prill and McElvain³. The reaction product was repeatedly extracted with chloroform. The extract not only showed strong blue fluorescence in the UV light, but also developed two very distinct Dragendorff-positive spots on the paper chromatogram (*R_f* 0.81, 0.64). These observations strongly suggest the formation of both the 3- and 5-substituted 1-methyl-2-pyridones. The dried chloroform extract was then chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. On successive elution with benzene-chloroform mixture (4:1) and chloroform, nudiflorine (II) and ricinidine (III) migrated out. Nudiflorine and ricinidine, thus obtained, were further purified by sublimation (at 100-10°/0.01 mm and 140-45°/0.01 mm). The synthetic products showed identical UV absorption [nudiflorine: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 206 (log ϵ , 4.28), 254 (log ϵ , 4.30), and 305 m μ (log ϵ , 3.77) and ricinidine: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 210 (log ϵ , 4.02), 234 (log ϵ , 3.69), and 334 m μ (log ϵ , 3.95)] and IR absorption [nudiflorine: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 2210 (-CN), 1660 (-NCO), and 1610 cm⁻¹ (-C=CH-) and ricinidine: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 2200 (-CN), 1650 (-NCO), and 1600 cm⁻¹ (-C=CH-)] with the respective authentic samples. The total yield obtained in this synthesis was 10%, comprising a mixture of 25% nudiflorine and 75% ricinidine. This ratio of the products is in conformity with the theoretical expectation. That of the two resonating structures, the one with 1, 2-double bond will have more contribution than that of the structure with 1, 6-double bond, in view of the presence of the strongly negative nitrile (I: X = CN) group at the 3-position.

* All the compounds mentioned in this communication gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

1. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1964, 1524.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2477.

3. "Organic Syntheses", 1935, Vol. XV, p. 41.

Pertinently, when the reaction was repeated separately with the methoiodide, instead of the methosulphate, of either 3-cyanopyridine or nicotinamide, only ricinidine and 1-methyl-2-pyridone-3-carboxamide were the products. Formation of only 1-methyl-3-substituted 2-pyridones in such cases may be ascribed to (i) the poor solubility of the methoiodides in water and (ii) its consequent slow hydrolysis at a low temperature, thus decreasing the overall yield of the products.

As was earlier suggested¹, this simultaneous synthesis of ricinidine and nudiflorine emphasises the probability of the natural occurrence of the former. Besides, the present findings not only support the biochemical results studied *in vivo* by Knox and Grossman⁷ but also corroborate the observations of Holman and Wiegand⁵, observed *in vitro*. Incidentally, the simultaneous production of these two compounds by chemical and enzymatic oxidation of nicotinonitrile methoiodide, as reported recently by Robinson and Cepurneek⁶, also confirms our biogenetic scheme.

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4. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1946, **166**, 391; 1947, **168**, 363.

5. *Biochem. J.*, 1948, **43**, 423.

6. *Phytochem.*, 1965, **4**, 75, 69.